

June 30, 2019

Effect of Silicon Application on Four Indigenous *Zea Mays* L. Varieties for Agro-Ecological Carbon Sequestration Potential in Nigeria

Author's Details: ⁽¹⁾ Ononyume, Martin Ogheneriruona ⁽²⁾ Edu, Esther Aja Bassey

⁽¹⁾⁽²⁾ Department of Plant and Ecological Studies, University of Calabar, P.M.B 1115, Calabar, Nigeria.

Abstract

Phytoliths have the ability to sequester carbon during their formation in plants as a result of absorption of soluble silicon in the form of monosilicic acid in their tissues. The effect of silicon application on phytolith production in four locally farmed varieties of Zea mays L. was investigated in the botanical garden, University of Calabar, Nigeria. Four levels of silicon 0 mg, 2500 mg, 5000 mg, and 7500 mg were added to soil in polythene bags in which seeds of four varieties of Z. mays L.; 91 SUWANI, TZL COMP 4, DT STR Y SYN 2 and IWO SYN C2 were planted. Wet oxidation method was used in the extraction of phytoliths from the leaves of the test plants. The concentration of silicon affected the phytolith quantity of the different varieties significantly ($P = 0.05$). The highest quantity of phytoliths was recorded in plants treated with 7500 mg silicon concentration. A total of 654 phytoliths were counted making up 26 morphotypes. Phytolith morphotypes were identified using the International Code for Phytolith Nomenclature (ICPN) descriptors. Phytolith morphotypes identified include cross, fusiform, rectangle and elongate which also ranked the highest in abundance with 91, 87, 85, and 70 phytoliths respectively in the four varieties while acicular, unciform, stellate and carinate morphotypes were amongst the least in abundance. Unidentified phytoliths comprised 1.53 percent of the total number of phytoliths counted. Four morphotypes; cross, cuneiform, elongate, and rectangle occurred in all four varieties studied. The results obtained from this study indicate that increased availability of silicon enhanced the phytolith production of the four varieties studied, therefore its implication in carbon sequestration. The opinion here is that the number of phytoliths will positively affect the amount of carbon occluded by the plant.
Keywords: Silicon, carbon, phytoliths, maize, concentration, sequestration, agro-ecology, Cross River

INTRODUCTION

The increase in the world concentration of CO₂ in the atmosphere is of great concern in recent times, the sequel to constant human activities of fossil fuel combustion, felling of trees which can serve as a carbon sink, burning of biological matter and rapid changes in the use of land resources (Marcias and Aberstain, 2010). This steady rise in global CO₂ levels could produce injurious changes in climate (Li *et al.*, 2013) and as such, various approaches are being sought after that can safely lessen and sequester carbon emissions including the injection of carbon into non-replenishable aquifers and salt water bodies (Hoffert *et al.*, 2002; Edu *et al.*, 2014). Nonetheless, these attempts to reinstitute carbon into the soil are transient and involve complex technicalities and economic problems (Rajendiran *et al.*, 2012). The organic carbon fraction present in the biomineralized silica features of land plants otherwise called phytolith occluded carbon (PhytOC) is a relatively fixed form of organic carbon that persists in the soil even after the decay of that vegetation (Parr and Sullivan, 2005).

Phytoliths are formed from the amassing of silica through biomineralization. Monosilicic acid (H₄SiO₄), is the dissolvable form of silicon that is present in the soil and is taken into the plant through the roots and translocated to the disparate portions or areas of the plant's organ through the xylem and phloem tissues. Consequently, the silica is stored up in the inner and outer cell structures of the aerial and subterranean parts of the plant (Song *et al.*, 2012). Major depositional sites for silica in the plant are the cell wall, cell lumen as well as the cell to cell spaces of the cortex (Rajendiran *et al.*, 2012). Silicon in the tissues of plants that are able to store it could range from 0.1 percent to 10 percent of the dry weight of the plant tissue which is highly dependent on the type of species (Epstein, 1999). Amid the process of soluble silicon uptake by the plants, carbon is covered up inside the phytoliths (Parr and Sullivan, 2005). These silica bodies or phytoliths confer different advantages on the plants and gives structural firmness and mechanical quality to the above ground

June 30, 2019

parts (Street-Perrot *et al.*, 2008; Namaganda *et al.*, 2009). Silica phytoliths help these plants to outlive numerous abiotic hassles, for example, salt stress, metal poisoning, nutritional irregularity, dry spell, radiation, elevated temperatures, and freezing (Ma and Yamaji, 2006) and additionally lessen the effect of biotic pressures, such as pest and fungal attack.

Maize in addition to being an economically important crop is known to be a prolific producer of phytoliths. The phytoliths inside the plant tissues acting as a sink for climatic CO₂ as phytOC. Numerous plant species collect silicon efficaciously as monosilicic acid, while other species can shut out successfully the drawing up of monosilicic acid. In spite of the fact that silicon is present in numerous plants, some trees, and members in the Family Poaceae and Cyperaceae (Mitani and Ma, 2005) are predominantly adjudged as the most efficient producers of phytoliths. The grasses are especially great at locking up carbon by means of silica biomineralization processes. Farming frameworks are essential as a carbon sequestration strategy because of the carbon stockpiling possibilities in the numerous plant species. The potential is by all accounts substantial; however, it has not been sufficiently recognized let alone exploited. If properly exploited can help in increasing comprehension of the level to which arable crops can lessen the acute nature of the forces of climate change and global warming. The aim of this research is to investigate the effect of silicon application on phytolith production in four locally farmed varieties of *Zea mays* L.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was carried out in the botanical garden, the University of Calabar, Nigeria within latitudes 4° 57' 11" North and longitudes 8° 20' 34" East. The experiment was a 4 x 4 factorial experiment. The design adopted for this research was a randomized complete block design (RCBD) and replication was done four times for each treatment, making a total of sixty-four experimental units. The four *Zea mays* L. varieties used in the study were collected from the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA) Ibadan, Nigeria. The soil used in the study for planting was fetched from the plot on which the experiment was set up. The fetched soil was filtered using a mesh with a pore size of 0.5 × 0.5 cm. This was to ensure that the sizeable and coarser fragments in the soil are excluded in order to boost the circulation of air. Sixty-four (64) polythene bags were filled with 20 kg of the sieved soil. Moist soil samples were collected from three arbitrary points in the plot using a tube auger and at a depth of 15 cm and mixed to create a composite sample. Physico-chemical analysis of the soil was done in the Department of Soil Science Laboratory, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Calabar, Nigeria. Five seeds each of the four varieties of *Z. mays* L. were sown in polythene bags and replicated four times. After germination, thinning was done to one plant per bag. Plants were treated with powdered silicon two weeks after germination by broadcasting around the plant and on the soil, thereafter watered into the soil. A revision to the wet oxidation method by Zuo and Lu, 2011 was adopted for phytolith extraction where 1 gram of dry sample from leaves of *Z. mays* L. were weighed using a sensitive weighing balance (to the nearest 0.01 milligram) and placed in a test tube. Then 5 ml (milliliters) of nitric acid (HNO₃) was measured with a syringe and added into the test tube containing the dry plant material. The test tube was then placed in a dry beaker and heated in a water bath at 80 ° C until the reaction ceased. The mixture in the test tube was centrifuged twice at 3000 rounds per minute for 5 minutes after which the supernatant in the mixture was separated using decantation. Then 10 % of Hydrochloric acid (HCl) was added to the precipitate in the test tube and then heated in a water bath at 80 ° C for 30 minutes thereafter centrifuged (Model 800D, Ocean Med+, England) at 3000 rounds per minute for 5 minutes and decantation of supernatant was done. Then 5 ml of nitric acid (HNO₃) was added into the test tube and heated. This was to ensure complete exclusion of all organic residues still present in the test tube. Centrifugation at 3000 rounds per minute for 5 minutes was repeated and the supernatant decanted. Thereafter 5 ml of concentrated hydrogen tetraoxosulphate (VI) acid (H₂SO₄) was added into the test tube using a pipette and heated for one hour at 80 ° C in a water bath. The resulting liquid in the test tube was left to cool to ambient temperature and then heated again in a water bath while hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) was gently added simultaneously to make the liquid limpid. This was then left to stand and cool to ambient temperature then

June 30, 2019

centrifuged 4 times at 3000 rounds per minute for 5 minutes and decantation was done. Phytoliths remained at the bottom of the tube and were dried at 70 ° C for 24 hours, and then weighed using a sensitive weighing balance Model JA3003, China, with an accuracy to 4 d.p (decimal place). Phytoliths were then mounted on glass slides, viewed with an optical light microscope (Model M82ES United Scope LLC, USA) at 2000× magnification and number of phytolith morphotypes viewed were counted and recorded. Photomicrographs were taken using Amscope MA 1000 camera, USA. Identification was done using the International Code for Phytolith Nomenclature (ICPN) key by Madella *et al.* (2005). Data obtained in this study were analyzed using Predictive Analytics Software (PASW)/(SPSS) Version 21 and means were separated using Duncan Multiple Range Test at P = 0.05.

RESULTS

Phytolith abundance

The effect of the various concentrations of silicon (0 mg, 2500 mg, 5000 mg, and 7500 mg) on the phytoliths produced in four *Z. mays* L. varieties are presented in Table 1. The results showed that there was a significant difference (P=0.05) in the phytolith quantity at the different concentrations of silicon in the varieties. TZL COMP 4 had the highest mean number of phytoliths produced (0.051 ± 0.001) followed by DT STR Y SYN 2 and IWO SYN C2 (0.049 ± 0.001) (Table 1), 91 SUWANI produced the least mean number of phytoliths (0.047 ± 0.001). Although there was no significant difference in the quantity of phytoliths produced by the different varieties, the highest amount of phytoliths was produced in plants treated with 7500 mg silicon concentration in all varieties, followed by plants treated with 5000 mg silicon concentration (Table 1).

June 30, 2019

Table 1: Physico-chemical properties of soil from the experimental plot in the botanical garden, university of Calabar, Nigeria.

Parameter	Value
pH	6.3
Organic carbon	1.02%
Total nitrogen	0.08%
Available phosphorus	31.25 mg/kg
Calcium	5.8 cmol/kg
Magnesium	1.0 cmol/kg
Potassium	0.15 cmol/kg
Sodium	0.09 cmol/kg
Aluminium	0.00 cmol/kg
Hydrogen ion	0.44 cmol/kg
Effective cation exchange capacity (ECEC)	7.19 cmol/kg
Base saturation (BS)	91.0 %
Clay	3.8 %
Silt	14.2 %
Sand	82.0 %
Silicon	481.9 mg/kg

June 30, 2019

Table 2: Mean phytolith produced (g) from leaves of four varieties of *Z. mays* L. at different levels of silicon concentration.

Variety	91 SUWANI	TZL COMP 4	DT STR Y SYN 2	IWO SYN C2
Concentration (mg)				
0	0.036±0.001 ^d	0.040±0.001 ^d	0.035±0.001 ^d	0.038±0.001 ^d
2500	0.040±0.001 ^c	0.042±0.001 ^c	0.045±0.001 ^c	0.042±0.001 ^c
5000	0.050±0.001 ^b	0.055±0.001 ^b	0.051±0.001 ^b	0.057±0.001 ^b
7500	0.063±0.001 ^a	0.067±0.001 ^a	0.068±0.001 ^a	0.061±0.001 ^a
Mean total	0.047±0.001	0.051±0.001	0.049±0.001	0.049±0.001

Note: values with the same superscript are not significantly different
P=0.05

Phytolith morphotypes

A total number of 654 phytoliths were counted from the mounted slides prepared from the leaves in all four varieties of *Z. mays* L., making up 26 identified morphotypes and 10 unidentified morphotypes. (Figures 1 and 2). The phytolith morphotypes identified include acicular, bilobate, cavate, carinate, clavate, cross, cuneiform, lanceolate, cylindrical, cylindrical polylobate, elongate, fusiform, globular, irregular, oblong, parallelepipedal bulliform, polyhedral, prickle, rectangle, rondel, stellate, saddle, square, tabular, trapeziform, and unciform. Cross shape, fusiform, rectangle, and elongate morphotypes ranked the highest in abundance with 91, 87, 85, and 70 phytoliths respectively in the four varieties (Figure 3) constituting a percentage abundance of 13.90 %, 13.30 %, 12.90 % and 10.70 % respectively of the total phytolith assemblage (Figure 4). Oblong, globular, cylindrical polylobate, cuneiform and cylindrical morphotypes ranked second in abundance with 63, 63, 45, 40 and 32 phytoliths respectively. Amongst the least abundant phytolith morphotypes are acicular, unciform, stellate, carinate, cavate with 1 each and polyhedral with 3 phytoliths in all the varieties. A total of 10 unidentified phytolith morphotypes were observed in the four varieties which made up 1.53 % of the total number of phytolith count. Of the total assemblage, four morphotypes occurred in all varieties; cross, cuneiform, elongate and rectangular morphotypes. While bilobate, fusiform, globular, oblong, polyhedral, rondel, saddle, trapeziform and unidentified morphotypes occurred in three varieties only (Figure 3).

June 30, 2019

Figure 1: Photomicrograph of identified phytolith morphotypes from leaves of test plants of *Z. mays* L.

(a) acicular, (b) bilobate, (c) carinate, (d) cavate, (e) cross, (f) clavate, (g) cuneiform, (h) cylindrical, (i) cylindrical polylobate, (j) elongate, (k) fusiform, (l) globular, (m) irregular, (n) oblong, (o) parallelepipedal, (p) polyhedral (q) lanceolate, (r) prickle, (s) stellate, (t) rectangle, (u) rondel, (v) saddle, (w) square, (x) tabular, (y) trapeziform, (z) unciform

June 30, 2019

Figure 2: Photomicrograph of unidentified phytolith morphotypes from leaves of test plants of *Z. mays* L.

June 30, 2019

Figure 3: Morphotype count of phytoliths from leaves of test plants of *Z. mays* L.

June 30, 2019

Figure 4: Percentage abundance of phytolith morphotypes from leaves of test plants of *Z. mays* L.

DISCUSSION

Phytolith production in the leaves of four varieties of *Z. mays* L studied increased with an increase in concentrations of silicon with the highest quantity produced at 7500 mg in all varieties (Table 1). The increment of phytolith production of *Z. mays* L on addition of silicon can be attributed to the fact that the crop is a monocot and it is classified as an accumulator, accumulating more than one percent of its dry weight of silicon (Epstein, 1999; Hodson *et al.*, 2005; Mitani and Ma, 2005). The quantity produced followed the same trend progressively in all four varieties at the various concentrations, but varietal differences were observed in

June 30, 2019

quantity (Deren, 2001; Ma and Takahashi, 2002). Henriet *et al.*, (2006) recorded similar results in banana, rice, and tomato. Ali *et al.*, (2009) reported that exogenous silicon application improved the silicon level in flag leaves of wheat. Andrade *et al.*, (2014) reported likewise in *Z. mays* L. The phytolith morphotypes observed from the leaves in the four varieties showed the range of diverse phytolith shapes that are possibly produced by *Z. mays* L. and the family *Poaceae*. The leaves contained morphotypes that were characterized based on shape amongst others into cross, rectangle, elongate, fusiform, saddle, bilobate, globular, cylindrical polylobate forms and rondels. The variation in shapes could possibly be genetic (Mulholland, 1990) or depending upon the area of the leaf epidermis the silicon is formed (Piperno, 2006). Piperno, (2006) reported that maize is characterized by cross shape phytoliths which supports the results of this study. Prychid *et al.*, (2004) also reported similar results in *Poa pratensis*, a member of the grass family. Hart *et al.*, (2007) reported the presence of rondels in maize and squash. Bilobate phytolith morphotypes were observed by Andrade *et al.*, (2014) in leaves of *Z. mays*.

CONCLUSION

The results obtained from this study indicate that increased availability of silicon enhanced the phytolith production of the four varieties studied, therefore its implication in carbon sequestration. The assumption here is that the number of phytoliths will positively affect the amount of carbon occluded by the plant that is, an increase in production will mean an increased rate of occlusion of carbon. Silicon, though not accepted by many as an essential element has proved beneficial in the growth and development of plants. The opportunity to enhance the sequestration of carbon through the uptake and storage of silicon especially in crops that are considered silicon accumulators like *Z. mays* L. needs to be exploited. Also, there is need to continually replenish the available silicon pool of the soil which can be achieved by recycling the straw or stover of the high accumulators of silicon in order to continue efficiently the production of phytoliths which will eventually impact on the carbon capture and storage potentials of agricultural crops.

Acknowledgment

The authors will like to thank the staff of the Botanical Garden, the University of Calabar for their support during the course of this research.

REFERENCES

- i. Ali, A., Basra, S. M. A., Ahmad, R. & Wahid, A. (2009). *Optimizing silicon application to improve salinity tolerance in wheat. Soil and Environment*, 28,136-144.
- ii. Andrade, F. A., Andrade, J. O., Andrade, C. G. T. J. & Miglioranza, E. (2014). *Accumulation of silicon and arrangement and shapes of silica bodies in corn leaves. Genetics and Molecular Research*, 13(1), 1690-1696.
- iii. Deren, C. W. (2001). *Plant genotype, silicon concentration, and silicon related responses. In: Datnoff L.E., Snyder G.H. & Korndorfer G.H. (eds.), Silicon in agriculture. Studies in Plant science*, 8. Amsterdam, Elsevier.
- iv. Edu, E. A., Nsirim, L. E., Ononyume, M. O. & Nkang, A. E. (2014). *Carbon credits assessment in a mixed mangrove forest vegetation of Cross River estuary, Nigeria. Asian Journal of Plant Science and Research*, 4(4), 1-12.
- v. Epstein, E. (1999). *Silicon. Annual Review of Plant Physiology and Plant Molecular Biology*, 50, 641-664.
- vi. Hart, J. P., Brumbach, H. J. & Lusteck, R. (2007). *Extending the phytolith evidence for early maize (Zea mays ssp. mays) and Squash (Curcubita sp.) in Central New York. American Antiquity*, 72(3), 563-583.

June 30, 2019

- vii. *Henriet, C., Draye, X., Oppitz, I., Swennen, R. & Delvaux, B. (2006). Effects, distribution and uptake of silicon in banana (Musa spp.) under controlled conditions. Plant and Soil, 287, 359-374.*
- viii. *Hodson, M. J., White, P. J., Mead, A. & Broadley, M. R. (2005). Phylogenetic variation in the silicon composition of plants. Annals of Botany, 96, 1027-1046.*
- ix. *Hoffert, M. I., Caldeira, K., Benford, G., Criswell, D. R., Green, C., Herzog, H., Jain, A. K., Kheshgi, H. J., Schlesinger, M. E., Volk, T. & Wigley, T. M. L. (2002). Advanced technology paths to global climate stability: energy for a greenhouse planet. Science, 298, 981-987.*
- x. *Li, Z. M., Song, Z. L. & Jiang, P. K. (2013). Biogeochemical sequestration of carbon within phytoliths of wetland plants: A case study of Xixi wetland, China. Chinese Science Bulletin, 58, 2480-2487.*
- xi. *Ma, J. F. & Takahashi, E. (2002). Soil, fertilizer, and plant silicon research in Japan. Amsterdam, Elsevier.*
- xii. *Ma, J. F. & Yamaji, N. (2006). Silicon uptake and accumulation in higher plants. Trends in Plant Science, 11(8), 392-397.*
- xiii. *Madella, M., Alexandre, A. & Ball, T. (2005). International Code for Phytolith Nomenclature 1.0. ICPN WORKING GROUP. Annals of Botany, 96, 253-260.*
- xiv. *Marcias, F. & Arbestain, M. C. (2010). Soil carbon sequestration in a changing global environment. Mitigation and Adaptation Strategies for Global Change, 15, 511-529.*
- xv. *Mitani, N. & Ma, J. F. (2005). Uptake system of silicon in different plant species. Journal of Experimental Botany, 56, 1255-1261*
- xvi. *Mulholland, S. C., Rapp, G., Ollendorf, A. L. & Regal, R. (1990). Variation in phytoliths within a population of corn (Mandan Yellow Flour). Canadian Journal of Botany, 68, 1638-1645.*
- xvii. *Namaganda, M., Lye, K. A., Friebe, B. & Heun, M. (2009). Leaf anatomical characteristics of Ugandan species of Festuca L. (Poaceae). South African Journal of Botany, 75, 52-59.*
- xviii. *Parr, J. F., & Sullivan, L. A. (2005). Soil carbon sequestration in phytoliths. Soil Biology and Biochemistry, 37, 117-124.*
- xix. *Piperno, D. R. (2006). Phytoliths: A Comprehensive Guide for Archaeologists and Paleoecologists. Lanham, MD: AltaMira Press.*
- xx. *Prychid, C. J., Rudall, P. J. & Gregory, M. (2004). Systematics and biology of silica bodies in Monocotyledons. Botanical Review, 69, 377-440.*
- xxi. *Rajendiran, S., Vassanda, M. C., Kundu, S. A., Dotaniya, M. L. & Subba, R. A. (2012). Role of phytolith occluded carbon of crop plants for enhancing soil carbon sequestration in agro-ecosystems. Current Science, 103, 911-920.*
- xxii. *Song, Z. L., Liu, H. Y., Si, Y. & Yin, Y. (2012). The production of phytoliths in China's grasslands: implications to the biogeochemical sequestration of atmospheric CO₂. Global Change Biology, 18, 3647-3653.*
- xxiii. *Street-Perrott, F. A., & Barker, P. A. (2008). Biogenic silica: a neglected component of the coupled global continental biogeochemical cycles of carbon and silicon. Earth Surface Processes and Landforms, 33, 1436-1457.*
- xxiv. *Zuo, X. X. & Lü, H. Y. (2011). Carbon sequestration within millet phytoliths from dry-farming of crops in China. Chinese Science Bulletin, 56, 3451-3456.*